

Reassessing Specialist Models: Risks in Fine-Tuning LLMs for Mental Health Task

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Abstract

Introduction: The increasing use of large language models (LLMs) in the medical domain underscores the need for responsible implementation, particularly when leveraging specialized clinical text embedders. While these embedders can enhance performance on domain-specific tasks, their reliance on smaller datasets introduces risks such as sensitivity to input variations and potential biases [1]. Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) further amplifies the importance of these embedders by using them to retrieve relevant information from knowledge bases, enabling LLMs to generate more factual and specialized outputs [2]. As platforms like Amazon Web Services streamline RAG pipelines for fine-tuning LLMs, the performance of embedders becomes critical to ensuring accuracy and scalability. This study evaluates embeddings generated by a domain-specific model (MentalBERT) and a general-purpose model (all-MiniLM-L6-v2) on mental health-related text from Reddit. Using dimensionality reduction and clustering, we assess which model better captures nuances indicated by subreddit labels, while exploring the implications for integrating LLMs and RAG into clinical applications. This comprehensive evaluation aims to build reliable, effective AI tools for mental health support while addressing the challenges posed by fine-tuning LLMs.

Methods: We utilized a dataset from the 'mdplus/Datathon2024' repository on Hugging Face, containing 54,412 Reddit posts labeled with mental health-related subreddits (e.g., r/SuicideWatch, r/Depression, r/Anxiety). Exploratory analysis revealed variability in text lengths and class imbalance, with "depression" being the most frequent label. Fixed-length embeddings were generated using MentalBERT (a domain-specific model) [3] and all-MiniLM-L6-v2 (a general-purpose model) and visualized via t-SNE for clustering. KMeans clustering (k=5) was applied to the t-SNE embeddings, and performance was evaluated using metrics such as Silhouette Score, Normalized Mutual Information (NMI), Adjusted Rand Index (ARI), and Purity Score. Visual comparisons via t-SNE scatter plots highlighted the strengths and limitations of each embedder, providing insights into their clustering effectiveness for mental health-related text.

Results: The dataset exhibits significant variability in post lengths, with an average of 178 words (SD = 237) and a median of 108. While most posts are concise, outliers, such as those in r/offmychest, often contain narrative-style posts that provide more context but may skew clustering results. Label distribution analysis revealed a class imbalance, with "depression" being the most frequent (17,500 posts) and "bipolar" the least represented (<8,000 posts), potentially biasing models toward dominant labels during clustering. Clustering performance metrics (Table 1) show that all-MiniLM-L6-v2 outperformed MentalBERT across all measures, with slightly higher Silhouette, NMI, ARI, and Purity Scores, though both models struggled to align clusters with true subreddit labels. Visualizations (Figure 1) confirm significant overlap between clusters and true labels, with only the "anxiety" class showing some distinctiveness in the latent space. While all-MiniLM-L6-v2 demonstrated better generalization, both models faced challenges in representing the nuances of informal, mental health-related text for unsupervised clustering tasks.

Table 1. Performance of K-Means Clustering on t-SNE of Text Embedding Models

Text Embedding Model	Silhouette Score	Normalized Mutual Information Score	Adjusted Rand Index (ARI)	Purity Score
MentalBERT (2D-tSNE; Kmeans nclust = 5)	0.308	0.057	0.037	0.347
all-MiniLM-L6-v2 (2D-tSNE; Kmeans nclust = 5)	0.350	0.120	0.085	0.409

Figure 1. t-SNE visualizations of embeddings: Plot A shows MentalBERT with KMeans clusters, Plot B shows MentalBERT with true labels, Plot C shows all-MiniLM-L6-v2 with KMeans clusters, and Plot D shows all-MiniLM-L6-v2 with true labels.

Conclusion: This study evaluated the effectiveness of clinical large language models (LLMs), specifically MentalBERT (domain-specific) and all-MiniLM-L6-v2 (general-purpose), in embedding and interpreting mental health-related text from Reddit's SuicideWatch and Mental Health communities. The findings revealed that neither model effectively clustered the data in alignment with true subreddit labels, as evidenced by low evaluation metrics such as Silhouette Score, NMI, ARI, and Purity Score. Although all-MiniLM-L6-v2 marginally outperformed MentalBERT, both models struggled to capture the nuanced and overlapping expressions of mental health conditions in the informal and diverse language of online forums. Factors such as label imbalance, variability in post lengths, and the models' focus on short-sentence tasks likely contributed to the underperformance, raising concerns about the use of specialized embedders in fine-tuning LLMs for clinical applications. This highlights the need for hybrid approaches that combine domain-specific insights with the robustness of general-purpose models, rigorous validation frameworks, and interdisciplinary collaboration to ensure ethical AI integration into mental health care. Future research should prioritize adaptable models, multimodal data incorporation [4], and ethical considerations to improve model reliability and patient safety in clinical settings.

References

1. J.-B. Excoffier, T. Roehr, A. Figueroa, J.-M. Papaioannou, K. Bressemer, and M. Ortala, “Generalist embedding models are better at short-context clinical semantic search than specialized embedding models,” Jan. 06, 2024, arXiv: arXiv:2401.01943. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2401.01943.
2. S. Siriwardhana, R. Weerasekera, E. Wen, T. Kaluarachchi, R. Rana, and S. Nanayakkara, “Improving the Domain Adaptation of Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) Models for Open Domain Question Answering,” *Trans. Assoc. Comput. Linguist.*, vol. 11, pp. 1–17, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1162/tacl_a_00530.
3. S. Ji, T. Zhang, L. Ansari, J. Fu, P. Tiwari, and E. Cambria, “MentalBERT: Publicly Available Pretrained Language Models for Mental Healthcare,” Oct. 29, 2021, arXiv: arXiv:2110.15621. Accessed: Nov. 13, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2110.15621>
4. S. Mangalik et al., “Robust language-based mental health assessments in time and space through social media,” Feb. 25, 2023, arXiv: arXiv:2302.12952. Accessed: Nov. 13, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2302.12952>